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ACTIVITIES OF DOMINICAN AND AUGUSTINIAN MISSIONARIES IN THE TERRITORY OF THE SAFAVID EMPIRE: INTERRELIGIOUS EXCHANGES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract.

The Dominican and Augustinian missionary orders penetrating into the Safavid lands, got special privileges from the Safavid kings and managed to build churches and monasteries here. These priests played an important role in translating the Bible and compiling dictionaries. Bartholomew of Podio and John of Florence who came to Azerbaijan in the 14th century, learned Turkish and Persian while in Italy. Jean-Baptiste Tavernier (2010), who visited Nakhchivan in 1650, describes in his travelogue that Latinization had so thoroughly penetrated this remote corner of Christianity that the Eastern Community of the Safavid Empire chanted the Dominican songs in Latin and offered the Latin Mass. *Relacao Verdadeira* (True Connection), a valuable source on the activities of the Augustinians in the territory of the Safavid Empire of Azerbaijan describes the visit of Shah Abbas I to the Church of St. Augustine in December 1608 together with the courtiers: “The beautifully decorated floor is covered with carpets and various aromatic substances (incenses) are burnt in church. The church is equipped with organs and other musical instruments. There are various divine paintings depicted on the altar of the Church: Paintings of the Virgin Mary and Jesus Christ – Our Savior. The choir plays local Portuguese music.” (Flannery, 2013, p. 120). The main purpose of this research is to study the role of the Dominican and Augustinian Churches in intercultural and interreligious relations. On the other hand, the presence of Catholics among the Muslim population changed the attitude of Shah Abbas I to the churches. The Shia clerics complained about missionaries that the Augustinians sent about 5,000-7,000 people to Hormuz to become Catholic. The Englishman Thomas Herbert visited the Safavid lands in 1627. His travelogue describes the churches and the espionage activities of the clergy. (Herbert, 2015, p.59) It is important to note that there were also priests who converted to Islam among Augustinians. One of the purposes of our study is to shed light on the causes of the conflict

between Catholic missionaries and the Safavid population based on the sources of the period.

Rezumat.

Ordinele misionare dominicane și augustine care pătrundeau în țările safavide au primit privilegii speciale de la regii safavizi și au reușit să construiască aici biserici și mănăstiri. Acești preoți au jucat un rol important în traducerea Bibliei și în compilarea dicționarelor. Bartolomeu din Podio și Ioan din Florența, care au venit în Azerbaidjan în secolul al XIV-lea, au învățat turca și persana în timp ce se aflau în Italia. Jean-Baptiste Tavernier (2010), care a vizitat Nakhchivan în 1650, descrie în jurnalul său de călătorie că latinizarea a pătruns atât de temeinic în acest colț îndepărtat al creștinismului, încât Comunitatea de Est a Imperiului Safavid a cântat cântecele dominicane în latină și a oferit Liturgia latină. Verdadeira (Adevărata legătură), o sursă valoroasă despre activitățile augustinienilor pe teritoriul Imperiului Safavid al Azerbaidjanului descrie vizita șahului Abbas I la Biserica Sf. Augustin în decembrie 1608 împreună cu curtenii: „Frumoasa podeaua decorată este acoperită cu covoare și diferite substanțe aromatice (tămâii) sunt arse în biserică. Biserica este dotată cu orgi și alte instrumente muzicale. Există diferite picturi divine reprezentate pe altarul Bisericii: Picturi ale Fecioarei Maria și Iisus Hristos - Mântuitorul nostru. Corul cântă muzică portugheză locală.” (Flannery, 2013, p. 120). Scopul principal al acestei cercetări este de a studia rolul bisericilor dominicane și augustine în relațiile interculturale și interreligioase. Pe de altă parte, prezența catolicilor în rândul populației musulmane a schimbat atitudinea șahului Abbas I față de biserici. Clericii șiți s-au plâns de misionari că augustinienii au trimis aproximativ 5.000-7.000 de oameni la Hormuz pentru a deveni catolici. Englezul Thomas Herbert a vizitat ținuturile safavide în 1627. Jurnalul său de călătorie descrie bisericile și activitățile de spionaj ale clerului. (Herbert, 2015, p.59) Este important de menționat că au existat și preoți care s-au convertit la islam printre augustinieni. Unul dintre scopurile studiului nostru este de a face lumină asupra cauzelor conflictului dintre misionarii catolici și populația safavidă pe baza surselor perioade

Keywords.

Safavid Empire, Catholic missionaries, Dominican Order, Augustinian Order.

Introduction

The colonial policy, which began with geographical discoveries, was carried out in parallel with the missionary policy. Although the missionaries came to the new lands disguised as poor priests, it was clear from their letters that they

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received financial support from the kings of Europe. It was exactly in the XVI-XVII centuries that the missionary policy of the Catholic Church in the Safavid Empire depended on the financial support and patronage of both popes and Catholic kings. In turn, the missionaries were going to be spies for their country.

Shah Abbas I (1587–1629) devoted the first ten years of his reign to strengthening domestic and foreign policy in order to wage a war against the Ottoman Empire. As a result, he allowed the missionary priests sent by Western countries as ambassadors to receive military assistance to settle in the lands of the Safavid Empire. (Mahmudov, 2006, p. 97) Thus, the members of the four major missionary organizations of Christendom managed to enter the Safavid palace as ambassadors. If, on the one hand, the aim was to create an alliance against the Ottoman Empire, so, on the other hand, the aim was to provide the early capitalist weaving enterprises created in Italy with raw materials at the expense of Azerbaijani silk.

As a result, the missionaries of one religion were rivals, not colleagues. For example, the Dominicans represented France and the Papacy, and the Augustinians represented the kings of Portugal and Spain at the Safavid palace. The Carmelites were of Italian and Spanish descent and settled in Isfahan as representatives of the Papacy. The Jesuits were defended by the kingdoms of France and Poland. (Quinn, 2015, p.76) The Safavid Empire was ruled by Islamic law and there was the death penalty for converting the Muslim population. In addition, since the Eastern Christians living in the Safavid territory were considered people of the Holy Book, their religions were not affected, and their lives and property were protected under Islamic law.

Seeing the impossibility of converting Muslims to Christianity, the Catholic missionaries drew attention to the Zoroastrians, Jews, Armenians and Georgians. In the interests of military alliance and trade, Shah Abbas I initially did not strictly control the relationship of non-Catholic Christians with the Papacy. The representatives of the Dominican missionary order, known as the "first inquisitors", arrived in Azerbaijan in the 13th century. (Hawting, 2005, p. 65) In the thirteenth century, the Mongol campaigns raised hopes for an alliance in the Papacy. In 1245, Pope Innocent IV sent Dominican ambassadors to the Ilkhanid palace. The Dominican priest Askelin arrived in Azerbaijan and stayed at the tent of Baiju Khan. (Guzman, 1971, p. 235) This is stated in the book "Historia Tartarorum", written by Simon, a Dominican priest from Saint Quentin. The Monk Simon pointed out an interesting fact that the Mongols were initially afraid that the priests would be accompanied by "Frankish troops" (crusaders). (Guzman, 1971, p. 233) For this reason, the Mongols conducted a serious interrogation of the Dominican priests. They thought that the crusaders had come to avenge the occupation of Poland and Hungary. Dominican priests were sentenced to death after it was revealed that this was not true. The reason

for this is that the priests recognize the Pope more than the Khan, and only the request of Baiju Noyon's wife saves them from death.

While in Tabriz, priest Askelin met with the Armenian priest Raban. Sources of that time confirm that the Armenians were spies for both Mongols and Christians. This is also reflected in Armenian sources. Kirakos from Ganja wrote that Raban had special privileges. (Bedrosian, 1986, p. 34) Everyone was afraid of him. He changed the religion of many people (Tatars). He built churches in Tabriz and Nakhchivan." Another Dominican priest, Podiolu Bartolomeo, who came to Maraga, was invited by Armenian monks to the monastery of Girna, and since then the monks of the monastery converted to Catholicism. In 1344, Armenian priests calling themselves the "Unitor brothers" adopted the Dominican sect and began to wear white according to the customs of Sacred Domingo. (Frazee, 2006, p. 130) The Dominicans helped the Armenians to receive financial support from the Papacy. During the reign of Shah Abbas I, Dominicans came in large numbers to the Safavid lands. These missionaries played an important role in the translation of the Bible and compilation of dictionaries. This article aims to shed light on the origins of that period of attempts by Dominican priests to spread Catholicism among the Armenian community of the Safavid empire, on the other hand, to explore their role in interreligious and intercultural dialogue.

At the end of the 16th century, members of the next Catholic missionary order, the Augustinians, entered the territory of the Azerbaijan Safavid Empire. The spread of this missionary order was closely associated with the colonial policy of Portugal and the Papacy. The journey of the Portuguese eastward brought them face to face with the Safavid Empire. On the other hand, with the opening of the sea route to India, an influx of European travelers to the lands of the "Great Sophie" began. The Portuguese, who blocked the Safavids' access to the Persian Gulf, founded the Goa prefecture in Hormuz in 1534. (Flannery, 2015, p. 87) It should be noted that the prefecture of Goa, created by the Portuguese, initially functioned as a bishopric. Goa became a metropolis in 1557 and controlled areas from the Cape of Good Hope to China. As the center of India, Estado also played a leading role in the spread of Christianity in Goa. It is known that there were 26 missionary orders in Goa, the most organized of which was the Order of Augustine. (Flannery, 2013, p. 89) In this study, we will find answers to these questions about the Augustinians. How did Portugal use the members of the Order of Augustine in its policy on Hormuz? How did the Augustinians contribute to intercultural development?

Activities of the Dominican Order in the Safavid Empire

During the reign of Shah Tahmasib I (1524-1576), the relations of the Dominican missionaries with the Armenians of Uchmuazdin expanded. In 1548, Catholicos V Stephen came to Rome at the invitation of Pope Paul III and converted to Catholicism. However, the Papacy provided only moral support to the Armenians. It should be noted that the intention of the Armenians converting to Catholicism was not only to receive financial assistance, but also to receive assistance in the fight against the Safavids with the support of the West. Proof of this is the negotiations between Catholicos Sebastian Michael and Pope Pius IV. In 1562, he sent a delegation to the papal palace, where it was ordered to announce that the Armenians had converted to Catholicism. (Chick & Matthee R, 2012, p. 345). In addition, the ambassadors were instructed to present to Pius IV a document confirming the meeting of Pope Sylvester with the Armenian Apostle Kirkor, which dates back to the IV century, and an appeal to the Pope to help the Armenians. During the meeting with the Pope, the envoys turned to the Pope for help, saying: "With your help, we will soon come out of slavery." (Adiele, 2017, p. 108) Sources say that the Armenians sent gifts to the Pope, including a ring, the remains of St. John's wort, a cross and a bottle of holy oil used in religious ceremonies. (Frazee, 2006, p. 113). Satisfied with the meeting with the Armenians, Pius IV sent a delegation to Uchmuazdin and Nakhchivan. The purpose of the delegation was to check if the Armenians were true Christians. But there was no news from the staff.

The travel notes of Jean Baptiste Tavernier are valuable resources for studying the living standards of Christians in the Safavid lands. Tavernier (2010) writes: "I never thought that I would find Christian churches so rich in Muslim countries. This patriarchal temple has not been so decorated in a century. However, this happened after the moment when Shah Abbas sent Armenians from Iran to trade and thus made them rich." J. B. Tavernier also describes the catholicos in Nakhchivan and writes that the Dominican priests carried out propaganda among the Armenians. Tavernier (2010) notes that the archbishop was appointed from Rome: "The man who is the archbishop goes to Rome and the Pope appoints him archbishop. The Archbishop lives in one of the most beautiful places in Asia."

During the reign of Shah Abbas II (1642-1666), the Armenians also turned to the Papal States for help. Charles Frazee (2006) writes that in 1662 the Armenian Catholicos of the Three Kingdoms Hakob IV and 25 bishops went to seek help from the West. The Dominicans welcomed them in Istanbul, and a document confirming their conversion to Catholicism was delivered to Rome.

During this period the Habsburgs openly supported the Dominicans. An example of this is the letter sent by Ferdinand III to Shah Abbas II on April 22, 1645. The emperor asked to allow Paolo Pyromalli to spread Catholicism and teach it in schools. At the same time, Ferdinand III sent a letter to Paolo Pyromalli. This letter was motivational. He later returned to Rome and translated the Bible into Armenian. Paolo Piromalli was elected Bishop of Nakhchivan in 1655. This appointment caused opposition among the population. The Carmelite priests note that Paolo Pyromalli's behavior was harsh and unbearable. (Chick & Matthee R, 2012, p. 320) Prior to his appointment, he was in Vienna and published articles criticizing the Armenians. One of the factors confirming the support of the Habsburgs is a letter from Leopold I in 1663 to Shah Abbas II introducing a Dominican priest named Antonio Taki. In 1682, Pope Sebastian Knab was appointed Bishop of Nakhchivan, and the Habsburgs again supported this priest. Sebastian Knab asked the Shah to open a Dominican monastery in Isfahan, and Shah Suleiman I agreed. (Frazee, 2006, p. 45)

I would like to point out that the Dominicans, along with the spread of Catholicism, have contributed to intercultural and interreligious dialogue. They were instrumental in translating the Bible and compiling dictionaries. Bartholomew Podio and John of Florence, who came to Azerbaijan in the 14th century, learned the Persian language while in Italy. John, a philologist, compiled the Persian Gospels, translated the words used into Latin and compiled a dictionary. (Halft, 2017, p. 584) Another linguist, a Dominican priest, traveler and diplomat, Beltramo Minyanelli, translated from Greek, Persian, Turkish and Arabic. In his book *Libellus*, he describes the differences between four languages: Greek and Persian - soft, gentle and feminine. Turkish is sharp, noisy and immature. Arabic is a very common, rich and complete language." In 1584, in Rome, the Grand Duke of Tuscany, Cardinal Ferdinando Medici, with the support of Pope Gregory XIII, opened a publishing house called *Stamperia Orientale Medicea* (published by Medici Oriental) to expand ties with the Safavids. This publishing house was provided with a large collection of manuscripts. Half of these collections belonged to Ignat Nehem, Bishop of Antioch, who came to Rome from Mardin. The rest of the manuscripts were collected by two brothers, Giovan Battista Vechetti and Ceralamo Vechetti, with the help of Dominican priests. Denis Halft (2017) writes that Paolo Pyromalli often took part in religious debates with the Safavid Prime Minister Khalifa Sultan (1592-1654). According to a report sent to Rome by a Dominican priest, he spent three years studying the language because he did not know Turkish or Persian, and wrote a treatise in Persian called "Risala der bayan-itikadat wa madhab-i kalimat Allah-i isavi" in Persian. He introduced him to the Sultan. In his report, Pyromalli apologized for not writing the treatise in Latin. Please note that the manuscript of this treatise is kept at the Vatican. (Halft, 2017, p. 521).

Activities of Augustinian missionaries in the Safavid Empire

The arrival of the first member of the Order of Saint Augustine priests to the Safavid lands coincided with the reign of Shah Mohammad Khudaband. According to sources, the king of Spain and Portugal sent an Armenian named Jao Battista to the Shah to congratulate him on his victory. In 1581 - the Ambassador stopped in Goa for a while and doubted his actions and the information he gave. He informed the ruler of Hormuz that the heir to the Shah, Hamza Mirza, was seriously ill and was cured by his Georgian wife (daughter of Alexander II). (Flannery, 2013, p. 164). The main suspicion of the ambassador's information was that Hamza Mirza converted to Christianity under the influence of his Georgian wife and asked the king to send a priest to convert Shah Mohammad Khudaband to Christianity. Of course, this information was fabricated by the Armenians. Priest Felix de Jesus Bilmeira Patre wrote in his report that after the ruler of Goa suspected an Armenian, Augustine, Somao de Moraes, who knew the Persian language, was sent to the Safavid palace along with an Armenian to deliver a letter to King Philip II. The records of Felix de Jesus also contain information that the Armenian tried to kill Moraes with a large knife. Mohammad Khudaband, who was on a military expedition, received the envoy in Khorasan, and Moraes returned to Goa in 1584 with the Safavid envoys.

Nicolaou de Melo became the second Augustinian priest to set foot on Safavid territory. Philip II instructed the governor of Goa to send someone capable of maintaining close ties with Shah Abbas I, who ascended the throne in 1587. In his report, Nicholas de Melo states that Shah Abbas I was very interested in Christianity and that the Shah presented him with a golden cross, adorned with precious stones, belonging to Prester John. (Flannery, 2013, p. 157) David Blow points out that the missionaries misrepresented the Safavid Shah; in fact, his tolerant behavior was motivated not by an interest in Christianity, but by a desire to find an ally. Believing that Shah Abbas I was the ideal ally, the priests sent a letter to Pope Clement VIII through Angelo Corrai, Anthony Shirley's translator. It should be noted that Shah Abbas I was preparing to send ambassadors to Europe at that time, and Nicolau de Melo also joined the delegation. However, he was arrested and burned in Russia. (Savory, 2007, p.128)

Antonio Gouvea' Relacam" is rich in information about the Safavid Empire. The Augustinian priests presented to Shah Abbas I a book about the life of Jesus, written by Jesuit Jerome Xavier in the palace of the Mongol ruler Akbar Shah, and the missionaries made every effort to convert the king to Christianity. This is clearly seen in the notes of Antonio de Gouvea. He described how he accompanied the king on the hunt and talked about the conversation between them: "I told Abbas I that among the qualities of a leader and a king he lacked

only Christianity. The king laughed and replied that only God knows what is in our hearts." (Flannery, 2010, p. 88)

In 1602, the monastery and the church of Augustine were opened in Isfahan. The Kingdom of Portugal donated an annual tax from the Congo trading post to the monastery. An anonymous letter in the Vatican archives says that Shah Abbas I paid all the expenses of the missionaries, first giving them a beautiful house and then a church. "Relação Verdadeira" (True Connection), a valuable source on Augustinians' activities in the Azerbaijan Safavid Empire, describes the visit of Shah Abbas I to the Augustine church in December 1608, accompanied by his courtiers: "Beautifully decorated, carpeted, smelled of various aromatic substances. On the altar of the church various divine images are placed: images of St. Mary, Jesus - our Savior. The church is equipped with organs and other musical instruments. The choir plays local Portuguese music." A document kept in the National Archives of Portugal says that "the monastery was built three years before the fall Hormuz." (Hartman, 1967, p.110). Although the exact location is not described, it is said to be near the Shah's palace. Augustine said that the Safavid courtier Ali Bey Shah told the priests about his visit to the church: "Several years ago, Muslims were prohibited from attending the church, so it was set on fire. Now they were not only allowed to enter the church, but the Shah himself entered here and allowed the slaves to be freed and sent to Christian lands." It is said that later Ali Bey came to the church and conveyed the Shah's decree. According to the decree, Muslims can convert to Christianity if they wish, but only if the clergy will not interfere with a Christian who wants to convert to Islam. In response, the missionaries declared that "they did not object to the king's decree. However, we are sad to see a Christian abandon his religion." (Flannery, 2013, p.106). We did not receive any other sources about the existence of this decree. John Flanner (2013) writes that only five Muslims converted to Christianity. These five were killed on the orders of Shah Abbas I. The reason is the complaint of the missionaries of the Shiite clergy. They told the shah that they had sent between 5,000 and 7,000 people to Hormuz to become Catholic, and the shah was angry at this. The Vatican archives contain a document dated 1622, which proves the murder of five people. But the letter from Antonio de Menezes to the Governor of Hormuz is also noteworthy. In this letter, he wrote that the Safavid side was worried that slaves would be sent to Hormuz to be baptized in water, and demanded to ban it. After expelling the Portuguese from Hormuz, Safavid Shah did not need the Catholic missionaries, and the decree which he signed was a heavy blow to the missionaries. It was said in the decree that a Christian who adopted Islam possessed the property of his relatives up to the seventh generations. By 1654, more than 50.000 Christian left the Christian faith. (Chick & Matthee R, 2012, p. 208)

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It should be noted that the priests of the Order of Augustine play an important role in interreligious and intercultural dialogue. Some of these priests even converted to Islam. However, the conversion to Islam by priest Antonio de Jesus is the most appalling in the Christian world. Because Antonio de Jesus not only converted to Islam, but also wrote anti-Christian commentaries. Exploring his life, Alberto Tiburcio (2017) notes that in 1695, Bishop Louis Marie Pidou de Sait wrote a letter to the Vatican saying that Augustus was an "unfaithful" inspired by Islam and was named Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam. According to the Dutch Oriental Company, Ali Gulu was a translator at the Jadid al-Islam Safavid palace. In the records of the Carmelites there is also information about this Augustinian priest. The Carmelite priests sent a letter to the Pope in Rome asking them to allow them to write and translate a work that contradicts Ali Gulu Jadid's comments and to hand it over to the Safavid Shah. The records of Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam are kept in the archives of the Vatican. Alberto Tiburcho translated these records, and it is clear from them that Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam voluntarily adopted this religion. (Tiburcio, 2017, p. 15).

During this period, the Papacy increased pressure on the Koran and Sharia. Quadagnoli, one of the main figures of the Society for the Spread of Faith, was known for his anti-Islamic rhetoric. He was also the first Arabic teacher to teach at La Sapienza University. Quadagnoli translated his book "Apology" into Arabic in 1637 and published it. In this book, he criticized the prophet Muhammad and called him a "hypocrite." On the other hand, he noted the similarities between the Koran and the Bible. It should be noted that the Pope was dissatisfied with Quadagnoli's identification of the Bible with Koran, and this book began to be criticized by the Vatican Palace. This book was also brought by missionaries to the Safavid lands. Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam wrote "The Work of Saif al-Mum & quot; in response to this book. It should be noted that the priests of the Order of Augustine play an important role in interreligious and intercultural dialogue. Some of these priests even converted to Islam. However, the conversion to Islam by priest Antonio de Jesus is the most appalling in the Christian world. Because Antonio de Jesus not only converted to Islam, but also wrote anti-Christian commentaries. Exploring his life, Alberto Tiburcio (2017) notes that in 1695, Bishop Louis Marie Pidou de Sait wrote a letter to the Vatican saying that Augustus was an "unfaithful" inspired by Islam and was named Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam. According to the Dutch Oriental Company, Ali Gulu was a translator at the Jadid al-Islam Safavid palace. In the records of the Carmelites there is also information about this Augustinian priest. The Carmelite priests sent a letter to the Pope in Rome asking them to allow them to write and translate a work that contradicts Ali Gulu Jadid's comments and to hand it over to the Safavid Shah. The records of Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam are kept in the archives of the Vatican. Alberto Tiburcho translated these records, and it is clear from them

that Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam voluntarily adopted this religion. (Tiburcio, 2017, p. 20). Only three copies of this work have been preserved. These copies are stored in Isfahan, Gum and Mashhad. Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam opposed the introduction of the critical image of the prophet Muhammad (peace and blessing) in the book of Guadagnoli "Apology", accusing him of ignorance of Arabic philology and spreading these misconceptions from Rome to India, Uzbekistan and the Maghreb countries as "assistants to Satan." Ali Kulu Jadid al-Islam proves that the Prophet of Islam is a true prophet, quoting examples from the Bible: "This innocent slave will issue many just laws and bear their sins above his shoulders. I'll give him a lot of kids." It should be noted that the priests of the Order of Augustine play an important role in interreligious and intercultural dialogue. Some of these priests even converted to Islam. However, the conversion to Islam by priest Antonio de Jesus is the most appalling in the Christian world. Because Antonio de Jesus not only converted to Islam, but also wrote anti-Christian commentaries. Exploring his life, Alberto Tiburcio (2017) notes that in 1695, Bishop Louis Marie Pidou de Sait wrote a letter to the Vatican saying that Augustus was an "unfaithful" inspired by Islam and was named Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam. According to the Dutch Oriental Company, Ali Gulu was a translator at the Jadid al-Islam Safavid palace. In the records of the Carmelites there is also information about this Augustinian priest. The Carmelite priests sent a letter to the Pope in Rome asking them to allow them to write and translate a work that contradicts Ali Gulu Jadid's comments and to hand it over to the Safavid Shah. The records of Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam are kept in the archives of the Vatican. Alberto Tiburcho translated these records, and it is clear from them that Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam voluntarily adopted this religion. (Tiburcio, 2017, p. 20).

Among the Augustinian priests, Simao de Moraes translated into Persian the books related to various Christian religions and the Augustinian book "De Doctrina Christiana". In 1635, Jose de Rosario, in a letter to the propaganda society of Fide (Society for the Distribution of Inanc), complained about the lack of books related to Christianity and languages. In 1638, the society sent to missionaries the translations of the book "Apologia de Christiana" into Latin and Arabic and "Summa Conciliarum".

Conclusion

As a result, neither the Dominican nor the Augustine orders of the Safavid Empire succeeded in converting Christians to Catholicism. Frustration in this failure, doubtless combined with the diplomatic interests of their country. The papacy and Western European countries provided financial support to the Dominican and Augustine missionaries and opened residences, churches, and monasteries throughout the Safavid Empire. However, the Safavid Empire,

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unable to get help from the Christian states, changed its policy and abolished the privileges granted to missionary priests. According to sources, only Ambrosio dos Anjos, one of the Augustinian priests, survived the plague in 1634. In a letter to Rome in 1635, Dominica de Luca, a representative of Rome, stated that she had remained in the monastery of Augustine. However, sources say that in 1639 the monastery was devastated and leased. (Flannery, 2013, p. 248)

It is clear from the sources that the members of the Dominican Order spread Catholicism mainly among the Armenian community of the Safavid Empire. Jean-Baptiste Tavernier (2010), who visited Nakhchivan in 1650, write about it in his travel book: 'There are 10 Christian Armenian convents between Nakhchivan and Julfa, both in the north and in the south, approximately 2-3 miles away from each other. These are submitted to the Pope and controlled by the Dominican clerics. As Armenians aren't religious enough, they send their children here to get religious education. These children learn Latin, Italian and necessary subjects for the work they will do.' (Tavernier, 2010, p.18) On the other hand, the research reveals that the Dominican missionaries were often involved in religious debates with Shia and Armenian clergymen. These disputes led to the emerging of tractates on Christianity compiled for the Safavid authorities.

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